

INSILICO IDENTIFICATION OF NOVEL DRUG AGAINST RHEUMATOID ARTHRITIS AND INFLAMMATORY COX 2 AND IL-1B INHIBITORS

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ABSTRACT

Inflammation is a biological response of the immune system that can be triggered by a variety of factors, including pathogens, damaged cells and toxic compounds. It is infectious and non-infectious agents and cell damage activates inflammatory cells and trigger inflammatory signaling pathways. Assessment of COX 2 binding affinity and active sites of ligand-receptor docking. Inhibitory activity of Lovastatin, Beta-glucan and Resveratrol with IL-1 β target. The 3D structure of the compounds which includes Beta-glucan, Lovastatin, Resveratrol. These selected ligands having anti- arthritic activity, anti- inflammatory activity anticancer etc. COX 2 proteins possess inflammatory activity.

Keywords:

Inflammation, inflammatory signaling pathways, docking, anti-arthritic and anti-inflammatory activity.

INTRODUCTION

Inflammation is characterized by the release of pro inflammatory mediators from pro-inflammatory cells, such as macrophages and monocytes, such as tumor necrosis factor (TNF), cytokines (IL-1 and IL-2), prostaglandin E₂, and nitric oxide (NO) [H. P. Rang.,2012]. Increased cyclooxygenase (COX)-2 expression and activity as well as inducible nitric oxide synthesis (iNOS) both had a significant impact on the inflammatory process. Anti-inflammatory medications could be required to terminate the inflammatory process and restore any tissues that have been harmed by the body's natural defenses. The use of currently available anti-inflammatory medications in clinical settings may be hindered by their negative effects (N. Mattison, 1988). The nonsteroidal anti-inflammatory medicines (NSAIDs), also known as COX-2 inhibitors, have been related to serious gastrointestinal problems such bleeding, ulceration, and other side effects include hypersensitivity reactions. The demand for non-invasive treatments that can reduce inflammation has increased as a result. (SR Suseem., 2011) For new anti-inflammatory compounds, researchers had turned to plants and mushrooms. Research has been done and a list of anti-inflammatory herbs and mushrooms has been created (N. Jose, 2002; M. Arawwawala, 2010).

MATERIALS AND METHODS

- Assessment of COX 2 binding affinity and active sites of ligand-receptor docking
- Inhibitory activity of Lovastatin, Beta-glucan and Resveratrol with IL-1 β target

LIGAND SELECTION

- Ligand selected from the PubChem database (<https://pubchem.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/>).
- The 3D structure of the compounds which includes Beta-glucan, Lovastatin, Resveratrol were retrieved from the PubChem database.
- These selected ligands having anti-arthritic activity, anti-inflammatory activity, anticancer etc. COX 2 protein possess inflammatory activity.

TARGET PROTEIN SELECTION AND PREPARATION

- The 3D structure of target protein COX-2 and Interleukin-1 β were retrieved from the PDB database (<https://www.rcsb.org/>) and it was prepared using Discovery Studio 2021.

DOCKING STUDIES

Docking studies for the target protein COX-2 and Interleukin-1 β and 3 compounds (ligands) were done using PyRx 0.8 software (Trott and Olson, 2010). The target protein was further prepared for docking studies using this software. All the ligands were uploaded using Open Babel option in the PyRx 0.8. The grid was generated and the docking studies were performed using Vina wizard option in the PyRx 0.8. The values of binding affinity were saved in XL file. The results were analyzed using Discovery Studio 2021 and the 2D & 3D docked images were taken. In the results, the lowest binding affinity indicates good result.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

In this phase we present results from the docking simulations performed between the potential bioactive compounds with targeted rheumatoid arthritis protein COX 2 and IL1 β for the development of new immune-modulators.

Assessment of COX 2 binding affinity and active sites of ligand-receptor docking

In the pathogenesis of rheumatoid arthritis, many receptors and antigens are involved, and the type of inflammatory response may also be different depending upon the initiation of autoimmune response (van de Stadt *et al.*, (2011) and Hanyecz *et al.*, (2014)). Different cytokines and receptors were involved in the triggering of RA, including cyclooxygenase 2 (COX-2), interleukin-1 β (IL-1 β), etc. Several herbal, natural, and synthetic source inhibitors were studied and reported (Shakeel *et al.*, 2022). However, a lack of comparison of the available inhibitors with natural ligands can lead to selection bias in a given biological system. To address this gap, RGL have been docked to identify the optimal choice molecule that can potentially lead to orally active drugs. *In silico* inhibition potential studies of LGR compounds against cyclooxygenase-2 were supported by performing molecular docking studies. Molecular docking has huge applications in drug discovery and development. All the title compounds were docked against target enzyme and all of them show different interactions with different residues of the active site.

The optimal molecular structure of Lovastatin, Beta-glucan and Resveratrol as inhibitor of cyclooxygenase 2 enzyme was determined. The minimum energy of ligands docked to the COX 2 enzyme active site was observed from the molecular model (Table 1). The active sites of COX 2 were cleaned up from any native ligand present and then Lovastatin, Beta-glucan and Resveratrol were docked into the binding site of COX 2. The docking scores towards protein COX 2 were -8.2 kcal/mol for Lovastatin, -7.7 kcal/mol for Beta-glucan and -7.7 kcal/mol for Resveratrol respectively indicating that all compounds have more interactions with COX 2.

The possible binding modes of Lovastatin, Beta-glucan and Resveratrol at COX 2 active sites have been shown in figure 1. The structurally and functionally important residues in the interactive sites of docked COX 2 were identified. Docking calculations of Lovastatin showed three interactions with TYR 136, GLY 135 and CYS 47 as important amino acid residues and bond distances of 5.33, 2.84 and 2.29 Å respectively, (Figure 1A).

The active site interactions with TYR 130, PRO 154, GLY 135, GLY 135, HIS 39, CYS 47, MET 48, SER 49 and CYS 36 as important amino acid residues and nine bond distances of 2.98, 2.60, 2.04, 2.84, 2.45, 2.51, 2.89, 1.67 and 2.38 Å respectively with Resveratrol ligand molecule (Figure 1B).

COX 2 protein residues LEU 152, PRO 153, GLY 135, PRO 156, HIS 39, CYS 36, CYS 36 and CYS 47 was formed eight bond distances of 4.94, 4.56, 2.26, 3.00, 2.50, 2.24, 4.85 and 4.38 Å respectively with Beta-glucan ligand molecule (Figure 1C). Lovastatin showed relatively good binding affinity as compared to other ligands. Docking results revealed that these ligands can enter the substrate-binding region of the active site. This theoretically explains the inhibitory effect of Lovastatin, Beta-glucan and Resveratrol on COX 2.

Table 1: Assessment of COX 2 binding affinity and active sites of ligand-receptor docking

S. NO	PubChem (CID)	Compound Name	Binding Affinity (Kcal/mol)	No. of Bonds	Interacting Residues	Bond Length (Å)
1	53232	Lovastatin	-8.2	3	TYR 136 GLY 135 CYS 47	5.33 2.84 2.29
2	445154	Resveratrol	-7.7	8	LEU 152 PRO 153	4.94 4.56

					GLY 135 PRO 156 HIS 39 CYS 36 CYS 36 CYS 47	2.26 3.00 2.50 2.24 4.85 4.38
3	71312131	Beta-glucan	-7.7	9	TYR 130 PRO 154 GLY 135 GLY 135 HIS 39 CYS 47 MET 48 SER 49 CYS 36	2.98 2.60 2.04 2.84 2.45 2.51 2.89 1.67 2.38

3.2. Inhibitory activity of Lovastatin, Beta-glucan and Resveratrol with IL-1 β target

Interleukin-1 β , one of the target in auto immune diseases like rheumatoid arthritis. Molecular docking of interleukin-1 β (IL-1 β) target proteins with three ligands were accomplished by PyRx 0.8 software (Trott and Olson, 2010). It focuses on designing active and exact inhibitors to treat inflammatory diseases. Molecular docking was performed in order to disclose the binding site of Lovastatin, Beta-glucan and Resveratrol in the protein. The results verified that adopted inhibitors were inside the active pocket sites of the target proteins with possible interactions. However, some have shown an important binding affinity with active site residues such as Lovastatin, Beta-glucan and Resveratrol. An inhibitor with a lower value (high in negative) of free binding energy is supposed to establish strong interaction on a specific active site; therefore, the results are ranked based on binding affinity, as shown in Table 2. The binding energy of Lovastatin, Beta-glucan and Resveratrol increased sequentially towards IL-1 β protein with the energy score of -6.7 kcal/mol, -6.4 kcal/mol and -5.9 kcal/mol indicating that Lovastatin had the strongest and most stable binding affinity toward IL-1 β . The 2D and 3D diagrams of the binding of Lovastatin, Beta-glucan and Resveratrol to IL-1 β are shown in figure 2.

As shown in the figure 2A, the binding site found in Lovastatin was basically composed of non-polar amino acids such as PRO 131, PHE 133, PHE 133 and GLY 136 with limited polar amino acids (charged or not) such as THR 137. Besides that, Lovastatin performs five bonds with the amino acids PRO 131, PHE 133, PHE 133, THR 137 and GLY 136 with bond lengths of 5.44, 3.86, 5.11, 1.80 and 2.29 Å, respectively.

As shown in the figure 2B, the binding site found in beta-glucan was basically composed of non-polar amino acids such as LEU 134 with polar amino acids (charged or not) such as GLU 25 and LYS 77. Besides that, Beta-glucan performs three bonds with the amino acids GLU 25 LEU 134 and LYS 77 with bond lengths of 3.70, 1.89 and 2.76 Å, respectively.

As shown in the figure 2C, the binding site found in resveratrol was basically composed of non-polar amino acids such as VAL 41, PHE 150, VAL 151, and LEU 134 with polar amino acids (charged or not) such as GLU 37, ARG 11, SER 152 and SER 153. Besides that, Beta-glucan performs three bonds with the amino acids GLU 37, VAL 41, ARG 11, PHE 150, VAL 151, SER 152 and SER 153 with bond lengths of 2.57, 4.96, 1.42, 1.94, 5.28, 2.52 and 2.70 Å, respectively.

These interactions reduced the energy required for binding, which increased the affinities between the active compounds and IL-1 β protein structure (PDB ID: 1ITB) to make them easier to bind. The verification results of molecular docking showed that Lovastatin was confirmed to be the active compound that most easily bound to the IL-1 β receptor, which is a natural IL-1 β inhibitor having curing potential and contain research value. Not only that, once experimental studies confirm that these active compounds can be effective in the RA model, they will be essential discoveries and provide more possibilities for drug development of IL-1 β inhibitors. Moreover, the remaining 2 active compounds were also relatively easy to bind to the IL-1 β receptor, and all had good affinities.

Table 2: Inhibitory activity of Lovastatin, Beta-glucan and Resveratrol with IL-1 β target

S.No	PubChem (CID)	Compound Name	Binding Affinity (Kcal/mol)	No. of Bonds	Interacting Residues	Bond Length(Å)
1	53232	Lovastatin	-6.7	5	PRO 131 PHE 133 PHE 133 THR 137 GLY 136	5.44 3.86 5.11 1.80 2.29
2	71312131	Beta-glucan	-6.4	3	GLU 25 LEU 134 LYS 77	3.70 1.89 2.76
3	445154	Resveratrol	-5.9	7	GLU 37 VAL 41 ARG 11 PHE 150 VAL 151 SER 152 SER 153	2.57 4.96 1.42 1.94 5.28 2.52 2.70

Cytoscape interaction network revealing that *C. caesia* may inhibit rheumatoid arthritis through different metabolic pathways. NFKB1, PRKCA, RAC1, STAT3, and TLR4 were identified as potential core targets while 13 compounds α -Terpineol, Ar-tumerone, 3,3,8,8-tetramethyl-tricyclo-oct-5-ene-5-propanoic acid (TPA), Rosifoliol, 2-Nonanone, Terpinen-4-ol, Dihydrocarveol, 5-Nonanone, Camphene, Linalool, Bornyl acetate, Camphor were identified as potential core compounds (12).

Elevated serum levels of IL-1 β have been reported in patients with rheumatoid arthritis (Chabaud *et al.*, 2001). Decreasing the expression levels of IL-1 β could decrease inflammation and facilitate the treatment of rheumatoid arthritis (Ruscitti *et al.*, 2015). The decrease in the activity of the ERK/STAT pathway induced by anti-IL-1 β was identified to protect rheumatoid arthritis rat against arthritic inflammation, possibly by inhibiting the IL-1 β -mediated activation of the NF- κ B signaling pathway (Yang *et al.*, 2019). The present results suggested that ligands mitigate IL-1 β may block the NF- κ B-mediated ERK/STAT1 signaling pathway may represent a potential therapeutic target for the treatment of rheumatoid arthritis. This cytokine is an important mediator of the inflammatory response, and is involved in a variety of cellular activities, including cell proliferation, differentiation, and apoptosis. The induction of cyclooxygenase-2 (PTGS2/COX2) by this cytokine in the central nervous system (CNS) is found to contribute to inflammatory pain hypersensitivity (Acro biosystems). From this study, its reported that Lovastatin, Beta-glucan and Resveratrol act as good inhibitor for rheumatoid arthritis causing receptors COX2 and IL-1 β . In future we lead this study to find the mechanistic action of ligands.

Summary and conclusion

Moreover, we docked the phytochemicals and examined their binding affinities with COX2 and IL-1 β proteins, which are over expressed in rheumatoid arthritis. The molecular docking analysis showed that Lovastatin, Beta-glucan and Resveratrol exhibited better binding affinities with EGFR COX2 and IL-1 β proteins. This result provides a strong ground for confirmation of the in vivo antiarthritic effect of *Pleurotus florida*.

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